

Gating strategy of ILC2 and ILC3

online repository file 3. A gating strategy to determine the abundance of lung ILC2 and ILC3. Lung ILC2 were identified as lineage (lin)⁻ CD3⁻ CD4⁻ CD45⁺ ICOS⁺ ST2⁺ GATA3⁺ cells, and lung ILC3 were identified as lin⁻ CD3⁻ CD4⁻ CD45⁺ ICOS⁺ GATA3⁻ RORgt⁺ cells.